

NAVIGATING THE ADVANTAGES AND CHALLENGES OF STARTING AN
ONLINE BUSINESS IN UZBEKISTAN AND THE IMPACTS OF THE GROWING
MARKET

O.A. Ashurbaev, Senior Lecturer, Millat Umidi University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

N. Umarxonova, Student, Millat Umidi University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Annotatsiya: Ушбу мақолада асосан Ўзбекистонда электрон тижоратни ташкил қилишда афзаллик ва камчилик томонлари, шунингдек ривожланаётган бозорга қандай таъсир қилаётганлигини турли статистикалар орқали таҳлил қилинади. Бундан ташқари халқаро ва маҳаллий электрон тижорат саноат орқали бизнесини амалга оширадиган кампанияларни даромадини, ривожланиши статистик маълумотлар орқали таққошлаш ва стратегияларини Ўзбекистонда тўғри амалга ошириш ўрганилади. Ўзбекистонда электрон тижоратни амалга оширишда дуч келадиган имкониятлар ва қийинчиларни ўрганишдан ташқари, Ўзбекистондаги электрон тижоратнинг ўсишини ўрганиш учун асосий фактлари келтиришда асосан 2018 йилдан бошлаб 2027 йилгача бўлган электрон тижоратнинг ўсишига боғлиқ бўлган статистикалардан фойдаланилади. Амалий таҳлилларни ўтказиш учун асосан 10 та мутахасисларда сўровнома ўтказиш ва тахминларни тўғри ёки нотўғрилигини исботлаш учун гипотезия тести ўтказилади. Ушбу мақолани асосий мақсади Ўзбекистондаги электрон тижоратнинг афзалликлари ва камчиликларни ўрганган ҳолда ушбу бизнесни ташкил қилиш яхши ёки ёмон бўлишини аниқлаш, ривожланаётган онлайн бизнесини ўсиб бораётган бозорга, мижозларнинг хатти-ҳаракатига таъсирини тадқиқ қилишдан иборатдир.

Kalit so'zlar: Afzalliklar, Kamchiliklar, Xalqaro va Mahalliy elektron tijorat kompaniyalari, O'zbekistondagi elektron tijorat, Uzum Market, AliExpress, Wildberries, Temu, Wolt, Yandex,

Аннотация: В этой статье в основном анализируются преимущества и недостатки электронной коммерции в Узбекистане, а также то, как она влияет на развивающийся рынок с помощью различных статистических данных. Кроме того, международные и местные компании электронной коммерции, ведущие свой бизнес через эту отрасль, будут изучать статистику доходов и развития, а также правильную реализацию своих стратегий в Узбекистане. Помимо изучения возможностей и проблем, с которыми сталкиваются при внедрении электронной коммерции в Узбекистане, основные факты для изучения роста электронной коммерции в Узбекистане в основном основаны на росте электронной коммерции с 2018 по 2027 год. Используются статистические данные. Для проведения практического анализа проводится опрос 10 экспертов и проверка гипотез, чтобы доказать, верны или неверны предположения. Основная цель данной статьи – определить, хорошо или плохо организовывать электронную коммерцию в Узбекистане, изучая ее преимущества и недостатки, а также исследовать влияние развивающегося онлайн-бизнеса на растущий рынок и поведение клиентов.

Ключевые слова: Электронная коммерция в Узбекистане, Преимущества и недостатки, Международные и местные компании электронной коммерции, Uzum Market, AliExpress, Wildberry, Temu, Wolt, Yandex, O LX.

Abstract: This article mainly analyzes the advantages and disadvantages of e-commerce in Uzbekistan, as well as how it affects the developing market through various statistics. In addition, international and local e-commerce companies that do their business through the industry will study the revenue and development statistics and the correct implementation of their strategies in Uzbekistan. In addition to studying the opportunities and challenges faced in the implementation of e-commerce in Uzbekistan, the main facts for studying the growth of e-commerce in Uzbekistan are mainly based on the growth of e-commerce from 2018 to 2027. statistics are used. To carry out practical analysis, a survey of 10 experts is conducted, and a hypothesis test is conducted to prove whether the assumptions are correct or incorrect. The main purpose of this article is to determine whether it is good or bad to organize e-commerce in Uzbekistan by studying its advantages and disadvantages and to research the impact of the developing online business on the growing market and customer behavior.

Key words: E-commerce in Uzbekistan, Advantages and Disadvantages, International and Local e-commerce companies, Uzum Market, AliExpress, Wildberries, Temu, Wolt, Yandex, OLX.

1.0

INTRODUCTION

This article focuses on the implementation of e-commerce in Uzbekistan and analyzes the advantages and disadvantages, as well as how it affects the growing market and customer behavior based on in-depth research. In addition, information is given on the basis of other written articles about the history and types of electronic commerce. Statistics from 2018 to 2027 were used to compare the performance of e-commerce in companies in developed countries and the comparison of these international companies with Uzbekistan, and the correct application of strategies was analyzed. In the next part, the opportunities and challenges that can be faced in the implementation of e-commerce are considered. Hypothesis and survey analyses are conducted to prove these given data with practical analysis. In the hypothesis, the correctness or inaccuracy of the prediction is examined through specific facts and statistics, and in the survey, 10 experts are conducted through docs.google.com/form/. At the end of the article, the given information will be analyzed, which one is good or bad in the implementation of this online business, decisions will be made, and the final conclusion will be given.

2.0. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section discusses the history and types of e-commerce, advantages and disadvantages, examples of international e-commerce companies, and information on e-commerce companies in Uzbekistan. In addition, the opportunities and difficulties encountered in the implementation of this online business in Uzbekistan are studied in depth with examples.

2.1. E-Commerce

According to Lutkevich (2020), This e-commerce refers primarily to various online business organizations that engage in the sale and purchase of their products or services. This business is mainly carried out with the help of technologies, for example, computers and internet networks. The basic understanding about this e-commerce shows that by doing this online commerce, one can buy all the necessary things even sitting at home, and it is not difficult for the retail sellers to enter this business.

•History of E-commerce

According to Kiriakidis (2016), Nowadays, almost all people are considered to have almost all knowledge about how to use this online commerce and how this business works and buy various products for themselves through this online commerce. It follows that till now this online commerce is available in almost all parts of the world; a brief explanation of the history of this online commerce shows that this business was first discovered in **1960**. In this year, researchers to improve electronic data exchange created the first system. but as the first online retailer, **Net Market was founded in 1994**, and this online retailer mainly sold **CDs** through its websites. After these years, the online trade industry began to develop dramatically and led to the founding of large companies such as **Amazon and Alibaba**. One of the most beneficial aspects of this e-commerce is that it reduces various costs.

• **Advantages and Disadvantages of E-Commerce**

Advantages - there are several advantages of this e-commerce, the first of which is the convenience of **24 hours and seven days a week**. Through this strategy, it provides many conveniences for customers to sell themselves. In addition, by **reducing costs**, this type of business does not require a specific location, which causes many cost reductions. Another advantage is that it is seles international trade, in which the seller has the opportunity to sell his products to people in other countries (MailChimp, 2023).

Disadvantages - of e-commerce are some limited customer service and **long delivery times**, which means that it takes at least **2-3 days** for your purchase to arrive, but **Amazon** It has the feature of delivery in **1 day** when the purchase is made as an exception. Another disadvantage is that the product may not look like the picture, so the buyer will not be satisfied with the product they have purchased, and the package will cause negotiations. The large number of competitors is also a disadvantage (MailChimp, 2023).

• **Types of E-commerce**

There are several types of electronic commerce. For example, as shown in the figure below, **B2C** is a business that focuses on selling products directly to consumers. **B2B**, on the other hand, refers to business-to-business sales of products to companies. **B2G** refers to the sale of products through business-to-government tenders. **C2C**, or consumer-to-consumer, business basically means selling products through different platforms (IndiaFilings, 2019).

Figure 1. Types of E-Commerce

2.2. Example of biggest E-commerce International companies

According to Lee (2022), There are several large online commerce companies around the world that are already considered successful. The chart below shows how these large online business companies rank in terms of revenue and competitiveness. **Amazon** is considered to be the first giant company in the field of online commerce and was founded in 1994 by Jeff Bezos, who started his first business as an online bookstore and later expanded his business scope. Amazon's company's revenue has been rising sharply over the years \$867.58 billion, reaching 11.8% growth in 2023 and reaching \$574.79 billion. This shows a one-year growth of \$36.85 billion. Another large company is **Walmart**, with a market value of 387.72 billion dollars, and at the same time, it is the second largest company in the United States. But it has enough reputation in online commerce considering its revenue is half that of Amazon company. The company that takes third place according to statistics is **Home Depot**. This company is also headquartered in America, and according to the market value, its revenue is almost equal to Walmart's, and it is 324.85 billion dollars. Online sales are especially important for home furnishings retail (Coppola, 2022).

Figure 2. Largest E-commerce companies

The company that occupies the fourth place after this company is **Alibaba**, which is headquartered in China. It was founded by Jack Ma and has a leading market capitalization of \$206.31 billion. Based on statistics, this company is growing rapidly, and its revenue will almost triple from 2018 to 2022 (Coppola, 2022). As an example of another online business, **Reliance Industries** in India is the fifth largest company in the world, with its main location in Mumbai. This company, due to several successes, caused its revenue to increase to \$206.01 billion in market value. The largest companies involved in online commerce are located mainly in America, and with other companies, it is possible to get enough information based on that picture below (Feldsher, 2024).

2.4. E-Commerce Market in Uzbekistan

• Executive Summary

According to KPMG (2023) ,A summary of the online commercial business established in Uzbekistan shows that, analyzing several statistics, **Retail sales** in Uzbekistan will reach \$14 billion in 2022, and by 2027, this figure is estimated to increase to \$19.6 billion. **E-commerce penetration** in Uzbekistan was 2.2% in 2022 but is expected to be around 9% and 11% by 2027 based on future projections. The total revenue of this **E-commerce** was \$311 million based on 2022 statistics. According to estimates, this indicator is expected to increase from \$1.8 to \$2.2 billion by 2027.

•Example and structure of E-commerce in Uzbekistan

The development of this online commercial business in Uzbekistan began in 2022, and **Uzum Market**, which is currently engaged in large-scale online business, was also established in 2022 year. This website is a major e-commerce site with 2.36 million visits, with customers placing the most orders, with its business primarily for delivery of various products and food. In 2023, Uzum reached its biggest milestone, making more than 1 million deliveries and establishing a 150,000-square-meter logistics center due to increased revenue. Based on the statistics of 2023, it has provided more than 800,000 product ranges for customers and acquired the popular payment platform "**Click.**" In addition, it bought another well-known platform, "**Payme,**" from TBC Bank to implement payment services (ecommerce, 2022).

Figure 3. Example of E-commerce companies in Uzbekistan

Company Name	Company Description	Downloads ¹ (mln)	Number of SKU ² 's	Warehouse Ownership	Number of Pick-up Points	Price per Order	Delivery Speed ³	Own BNPL Solutions
Uzum	A digital ecosystem which includes services for online shopping (marketplace), fintech solutions, payments and food delivery	13.1	500,000	Yes	500 ⁴	<u>Within & Outside Tashkent</u> — For orders up to \$43, the delivery cost is a standard fee of \$2.6 — Above \$43, delivery is free — Free delivery to Uzum Market pickup points	<u>Within Tashkent</u> — Same day delivery <u>Outside Tashkent</u> — Next day delivery	Yes
Zood	Zood is a digital lending platform, that provides a holistic ecosystem encompassing FinTech (ZoodPay), E-commerce (ZoodMall), and E-logistics services (ZoodShip operate by Fargo), with lending at the core of its operations	1.2 ⁵	6 mln ⁶	No ⁷	30 + 250 lockers	— Free delivery to pickup points and lockers for local and cross border	<u>Within Tashkent</u> — Same day delivery <u>Outside Tashkent</u> — Next day delivery	Yes
Mediapark	Marketplace for home appliances and electronics, operating an extensive network of 33 stores throughout the Republic of Uzbekistan	0.46 ⁸	NA ²	No	NA	<u>Within Tashkent</u> — Up to \$87.8: \$2.6/ Above \$87.8 Free <u>Outside Tashkent (up to 80 km from Tashkent city)</u> — Within a radius of 35 km: \$6.6 — Between 35 and 50 km: \$8.3 — Beyond 50 km: \$8.3 + \$0.2 per each additional km of travel	<u>Within Tashkent</u> — Within 24 hours <u>Outside Tashkent</u> — Within 72 hours (3 business days)	NA

According to Zuhra Otakuzieva and Ulugbek Nortozhiev (2024), Another e-commerce company established in Uzbekistan is **AliExpress**, which has achieved sufficient reputation. In addition, **Wildberries** is a large Russian e-commerce organization that entered Uzbekistan in 2022. These established companies use social networks like Telegram, Instagram, and other platforms to carry out their business. **OLX** also conducts online trading business, but the difference is that it mainly deals with individual trades. Many companies and banks use this OLX to offer

their services to their customers through cooperation. Later, the **Unisavdo platform** was established to carry out this online trade, and later it was planned to turn it into a large electronic market by 2025. Currently, there are several such e-commerce websites, such as **Temu, Wolt**, etc. However, these have not yet been determined by precise statistics. In 2022, the **Tradeuz.com** platform was established, helping small and medium-sized domestic online businesses to sell their products in other countries.

2.5. Opportunities and Drawbacks E-commerce in Uzbekistan industry

Opportunities - There are several options for organizing online commerce in Uzbekistan. It will be possible to include the possibility of paying in installments in these options. Using this strategy will help attract customers with lower family incomes and increase sales in Uzbekistan. Moreover, the frequency of orders may increase as online commerce from Uzbekistan develops day by day. will have the right to sell their goods in all regions of Uzbekistan in online commerce. In this online business, **online payment** is also implemented, so it does not cause many problems. When it comes to the possibilities of meeting the demands of customers, the first of these is to offer competitive prices, in which people in Uzbekistan are more sensitive to prices compared to other countries, so it is possible to turn these people into potential customers through **constant discounts and low prices**. In addition to offering a wide **range of products**, For example, **Uzum Market** has more than 500,000 product types on its site, and the speed of delivery also helps to satisfy customers. Due to the fact that it is organized in a flexible payment system, online payment has created many opportunities because it is considered convenient and safe (LLOYDS BANK, 2017).

Drawbacks - In addition to the possibilities of electronic commerce in Uzbekistan, there are also various limitations. These restrictions lead to a reduction in potential customers by delaying delivery of products to customers in distant locations due to **various problems in the logistics and infrastructure** used for delivery when viewed by the supply side. Other limitations are some of the limitations imposed on the infrastructure, including the **lack of internet**, which can cause various problems with connectivity. Financial services also have different restrictions, for example, **different laws issued** by the state, and different costs may arise from making payments to them. There are also **several restrictions** imposed on customers by demand, and customers are afraid to submit their details online due to the rise of fraudsters and the possibility of identity theft during online payments. Even **consumer behavior is hindering** online commerce. For example, Uzbekistan may face various challenges through the introduction of various new technologies and slow adoption of customers. Due to the various **restrictions imposed on Internet access**, Uzbekistan constantly prevents people from going online, which leads to a decrease in potential customers. People do not know how to use online shopping platforms due to the **low development of technology literacy**, which also causes a decrease in customers (KPMG, 2023).

3.0. RESEARCH METHODS

The main purpose of this article is to study the advantages and disadvantages of e-commerce in Uzbekistan, as well as to find out how it affects the developing market by analyzing the challenges and opportunities faced when starting e-commerce. Primary and Secondary research methodology was used in this analysis and statistical study. All the information presented in the

article is provided using reliable sources, and statistical information on e-commerce in Uzbekistan from 2018 to 2027, based on future forecasts, was used mainly from Google Scholar. The purpose of using this information is to find out how e-commerce is developing in Uzbekistan and to study the impact on the market by providing specific facts. Also, a question-and-answer session was held to conduct practical analysis in the article. This survey was conducted primarily among 10 experts via Google Docs, docs.google.com/form/. In the next practical analysis made in the article, that is, for the implementation of the hypothesis, statistical information was obtained from reliable sources, company websites, and various other sites.

4.0. HYPOTHESES AND ASSUMPTION

Hypothesis: E-commerce in Uzbekistan is developing year by year; according to estimates, it will grow by 11% by the end of 2027, which will have a positive effect on customer behavior, and some important factors for development are influencing, which will make the business to develop is creating an opportunity.

Table 1. In the following table, the **key facts related to Uzbekistan**, for example, population, e-commerce and retail market size, GDP, internet users, banking and internet penetrations, and other necessary information are defined in the form of percentage and US dollars. These statistics were analyzed in **July 2023**.

Key facts in UZB	Indicator (% or \$)
1. Population of Uzbekistan	36,372 ths
2. Population aged 15-39 (total population 40%)	14,393 ths
3. Internet users	23,533 ths
4. Retail market in Uzb	\$14 billion
5. E-commerce market size	\$311 million
6. E-commerce retail market	2.2%
6. Real GDP growth rate	5.7%
7. Inflation rate	12.3%
8. Unemployment rate	8.9%
9. GDP per capital	2,256
10. Banking and Internet penetration	Banking 49% Internet 77%

In the following statistical indicator illustrate the forecast of the **growth of the e-commerce market** from year to year. These figures show the low and high estimates for the period up to 2027.

Figure 4.

Growth of the E-commerce market in Uzbekistan (2018 to 2027)

It can be seen from the following statistics that an important part of the development of e-commerce is state support. State-side strategic initiatives for e-commerce will require government support for regulatory efforts such as enabling e-commerce to comply with all state laws, for example. E-commerce that is not implemented within the framework of this legal framework and law will not be successful.

Figure 5. The main factor affecting Uzbekistan's e-commerce.

The growth of Internet users in Uzbekistan will help increase competition in the market and increase potential customers.

Figure 6.
Growing
Internet

level of
Penetration

Conclusion of Hypothesis Testing

The hypothesis is true based on the findings above, from these data, it can be seen that the retail market size is \$14 billion, and the e-commerce market size is \$311 million. Although this e-commerce is not yet developed, it shows great indicators from year to year; that is, according to statistical analysis, the forecast of Internet access by the end of 2027 is 87%, when analyzed according to GDP, 57% of consumer spending, and the volume of retail trade, and it is estimated to be \$19.6 billion. This development does not affect the perception of retail markets. In addition, according to the above statistics, several factors help the development and strengthening of e-commerce in Uzbekistan, the first of which is economic growth, urbanization due to changes in shopping habits, and lifestyle changes in 2022. 'reportedly increased by 50%. Additionally, the growth of gross domestic products experienced a 5% boost. In addition, considering the influence of other factors, this increase in the level of access to the Internet will help to increase the competition in the market and expand the potential customer base. According to statistics, it can be seen that it has increased to 81% in 2024, and this figure may reach 87% by 2027. It can be seen that the development of e-commerce has a positive effect on customer behavior, and the income of e-commerce increases.

5.0. SURVEY

The specific purpose of conducting this survey includes the determination of the correctness or falsity of the given statistical data through clear analysis and question answers. This survey will conduct is mainly 10 or more experts. This survey is done through docs.google.com/form/. In addition, the questions of this survey are mainly used to clearly analyze the good and bad sides of the increasingly developing e-commerce in Uzbekistan, its impact on customer behavior, and the impact of various factors on development. Another purpose of conducting this survey is that for new business managers who want to start an online business, it can help them to analyze whether the business is suitable or not and to decide whether it will be successful or not. This questionnaire contains 11 specific questions.

6.0. COLLECTING, ORGANIZING AND ANALYZING THE DATA

The analysis of the conducted survey shows that in this survey mainly 10 experts worked and presented their opinions. This survey is made up of 11 specific questions, mainly to determine the opportunities and shortcomings that may be encountered in establishing an online business in Uzbekistan, the impact of e-commerce that is developing day by day on customer behavior, and other topics. survey was conducted, including. In this survey, **80% of people are 18-20 years old, and 20% are 27+ people**. The second question in the survey was about information and how much knowledge you have about e-commerce. Based on this question, it can be said that the low level

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of knowledge about technology in Uzbekistan affects the fact that they have more information about electronic commerce. In the next question, **80%** of people said yes, but **20%** of people said no. Therefore, e-commerce can attract more price-sensitive potential customers by offering more discounts. In the third question of the survey, when asked what problems they may face in the implementation of e-commerce in Uzbekistan, **40%** of people said that access to capital, **30%** of people said that it would affect legal regulations, and another **30%** of people said that it would lead to more difficulties in gaining the trust of customers. came to a conclusion. The next question asked of the customers is how the growth of e-commerce in Uzbekistan will affect consumers in 5 years. **80%** of people agreed that it will cause more changes because of more convenience; more customers may prefer to use online business through the convenience of delivery. and another **10%** decided that there would be moderate change and almost no change.

Pie chart 1. Uzbekistan e-commerce impact customer behaviour

Pie chart 2. Advantages of conducting online business in UZB

Pie chart 3. Diasadvantages of conducting online business in UZB

Pie chart 4. Rate the current digital infrastructure

In the next question of the survey, what are the advantages of e-commerce for entrepreneurs who want to start their own business? According to people's opinions, **40%** of people considered the growing market demand as an advantage, and **10%** of the survey participants said that it costs less than offline business. and another **40%** of participants consider the benefits of e-commerce to reach more potential customers faster. It follows that in establishing an e-commerce, mainly the high demand in the market and having more customers can make the business successful. **70%** of experts believe that digital payment solutions are very important for the growth of e-commerce, and **30%** think that it may be more important. When asked which sectors of e-commerce in Uzbekistan are important and create more opportunities, **80%** of experts agreed with food delivery, which means that the online business sector that brings the most income for online business is food. delivery is considered. **50%** of the experts said that they would support the development of online business, and the other **50%** decided that they would oppose it. survey analyses showed the above indicators.

7.0. DISCUSSION

When discussing all the information presented in this article, first of all, the article mainly examines the shortcomings and opportunities of starting and implementing e-commerce in Uzbekistan and how the development of online business affects the growing market. was considered with In addition, the history and origin of this electronic commerce were studied. The purpose of this analysis is to determine whether a thorough understanding of this business is beneficial for anyone aspiring to start their own business. and considering the **advantages and disadvantages** of implementing e-commerce in Uzbekistan, considering the articles written by some specialists, the good side of this online business is that it works non-stop for 24 hours, the ease of entering this e-commerce, and the high demand of customers. It was estimated that it could be done. In addition, due to the large number of types of e-commerce, all were considered based on specific analysis. In the article, considering strategies for increasing the income of successful e-commerce in another country, the income of **Amazon** \$867.58 billion, which is considered a giant in this online business, was analyzed through various searches. As an example, the statistics of other similar companies, **Walmart** \$387.72 billion, **Home Depot** \$324.85 billion, **Alibaba** \$206.31 billion, and **Reliance Industries**, were considered. After that, the statistics of electronic commerce in Uzbekistan were presented, and the income and strategy of **Uzum Market** 2.36 million visits, **Aliexpress**, **Wildberries**, and **OLX**, which are in the first place, and Temu and Wolt, which are new to the online business, were considered for the example of online business. . For this purpose, these international and local companies were reviewed to find out how e-commerce is developing in Uzbekistan. In the next part, by conducting **Hypothesis and Survey** analysis, specific decisions were made by conducting a survey of experts and accurate statistics in order to verify the information presented. The analysis of the conducted survey shows that in this survey mainly 10 experts worked and presented their opinions. This survey is made up of 11 specific questions, mainly to determine the opportunities and shortcomings that may be encountered in establishing an online business in Uzbekistan, the impact of e-commerce that is developing day by day on customer behavior, and other topics.

Decision making

In this article, in the implementation of this decision, first of all, it was decided that it is good or bad to implement this business through statistics and various in-depth analyses for the

implementation of e-commerce in Uzbekistan. This shows that nowadays, due to the fact that e-commerce provides various conveniences to the customers, the demand for this business is increasing, and it is developing day by day. considering that if this business is implemented, it will be possible to face many problems due to strong competition. For example, to gain the trust of customers, it is necessary to act more truthfully. By analyzing other developed companies, for example, Amazon, which strategy helped them to increase their income? If 1-day delivery is implemented in Uzbekistan, it will be possible to achieve great development like this company in the future. According to the analysis of 2022, the total income of e-commerce in Uzbekistan was **\$311 million**, but this indicator is planned to increase to **\$1.8** and **\$2.2 billion** by 2027. According to the hypothesis analysis, if this increase is realized, it is estimated that various factors will cause a positive impact on customer behavior and growth, and this assumption is proven correct by statistics. It follows that the implementation of online lines will become the need of the hour in the future and can help in faster revenue growth. In the survey analysis by [Google.docs.com](https://docs.google.com), it can be seen that almost **80%** of people bought products online, and this figure may be higher later, so this business implementation shows effective results!!!.

8.0. CONCLUSION

In this article, the conclusion shows that through the analysis of several data and statistics, the positive and negative aspects of the implementation of e-commerce in Uzbekistan were considered. Through hypothesis analysis, predict that various factors will cause the growth of electronic commerce and have a positive effect on customer behavior, and confirm that this prediction is correct through statistics. Due to the development of technology, it also affects the number of people using the Internet. According to the analysis of 2022, the increase of these users, which are shown to be used by 23,553 thousand people, will greatly affect the development of e-commerce in Uzbekistan. In addition, the article reviewed the statistics of companies in the international and local e-commerce industry based on research findings and concluded what strategies to implement for the development of local companies. In the survey analysis, a survey was conducted with 11 experts, as a result of which the implementation of online business was carried out based on specific opinions. According to the results, 40% of the experts defined the advantages of online business as market demand, and another 80% of people rated e-commerce as very good. The conclusion based on the analysis of this article means that face various problems in opening any business, but by doing everything correctly and with quality, achieve success, as well as this electronic commerce.

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